

Simulation of Charging Time Controller using Arduino

Arun Francis G^[1], Chandru L^[2], Arun Kumar B^[3], Nithesh Kumar R^[4], Narendran S^[5]

[1] Assistant Professor, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Karpagam College of Engineering, Coimbatore, India.

[2] Student, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Karpagam College of Engineering, Coimbatore, India.

[3] Student, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Karpagam College of Engineering, Coimbatore, India.

[4] Student, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Karpagam College of Engineering, Coimbatore, India.

[5] Student, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Karpagam College of Engineering, Coimbatore, India

Correspondence: ja.arunji@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This paper titled "Simulation of Charging Time Controller using Arduino," allows you to monitor the amount of time your phone's battery charges. In general, cell phones charge in a few hours; however, after a year, users can notice that the charging period is longer than when the mobile was new. This is because the battery's number of life cycles decreases. Since the cell phone has become an integral part of our lives, the majority of users charge their phones at night. So that their phones are completely charged when they wake up. Even after the charge is complete, the user can forget to switch off the power supply. This form of overcharging shortens the battery's lifespan. When advanced software detects that the battery is fully charged, it disconnects the power supply to the battery but not completely; this charging state is referred to as trickle charge. To get around this, you can use a "charging time controller." You don't have to worry about your smartphone after charging because the power supply to the battery is automatically disconnected. As a result, you won't have to wake up early in the morning to charge your computer or late at night to turn it off. Arduino is the brains behind this idea. Calculate the amount of time your battery would need to be charged and enter it into the LCD using an encoder. It will be disconnected using a relay once the charging time has expired. Consider the following scenario: it is 10 p.m. You just need to charge your phone for three hours; you don't need to get up at 1 a.m. to turn it off. The LCD monitor can be set to 3 hours to ensure that it is disconnected after charging.

KEYWORDS: Mobile phone charging, Arduino, Timing control, LCD, Rotary encoder.

INTRODUCTION

The mobile phone has become an indispensable part of our lives. The battery in a cell phone is extremely important. In recent years, every smartphone has included a built-in battery. As a result, it's important to keep your phone's battery charged. The majority of smartphone batteries are lithium ion, which aids in quick charging and provides a small size. Lithium ions, as their name implies, are the highest performing ions. When exposed to high temperatures, lithium-ion batteries can be damaged and perform poorly. If your computer is in contact with the back case when charging, there may be insufficient room to dissipate heat. The battery's heat can also have an impact. We've recently heard on the internet that some smartphones have been exploding due to overcharging or due to the heat that occurs in the battery.

We use our phones so much that they die after around 18 – 20 hours of use. Unless your phone's battery is a 5000 mAh powerhouse that was just unboxed. Most people charge their devices at night before going to bed, so that when they wake up, they will have a fully charged battery. The big concern arises, Is it really in need to keep the mobile plugged in even after the charge is 100%?

If you can't find time to charge your battery

during the day, leaving it plugged in overnight is often appropriate. Since your smart phones are intelligent enough to cut off power from the charging adapter to the battery when the unit reaches 100% charge. Every cell phone consumes power even when fully charged because it operates 24 hours a day, seven days a week. When your battery is down to 99 percent, it's time to replace it. Now, a phone should allow the battery to charge if the battery is less than 100 percent charged, according to simple phone rules. As a result, the phone begins to charge once more. As a result, your smart phone has a problem with this loop of jumping between 99 and 100 percent. One of the disadvantages of charging the battery even after it has reached 100% capacity is that the battery's cycle count is reduced, reducing the battery's lifespan.

Figure 1. *Issue caused due to overcharging of battery*

The battery's lifespan is determined by the amount of cycles it has completed. Temperature plays an important role in deciding how long a battery lasts. The temperature of the battery will reach dangerously high levels, reducing the battery's lifespan. Let's take a look at the functionality of both the current and proposed system.

EXISTING SYSTEM

Normal Charger

Almost all mobile phone chargers these days are superfast chargers. The charger's size is

adequate, and the charging speed per hour is adequate when compared to solar and wireless chargers, but when it comes to the consumer, these three types of chargers can cause problems if they are repeatedly overcharged. Since almost every user is busy at work, particularly in the morning, they want their mobile to be fully charged, so the majority of users turn on the adapter before going to bed so that it is fully charged in the morning. Because of the inbuilt software, this overcharging may not trigger any issues at first. But, as the day goes by, this overcharging decreases the amount of charging times and eventually contributes to battery loss.

Wireless Charger

Wireless charging is becoming increasingly common these days, with most of the major cell phone manufacturers releasing phones that support it. The term "wireless charger" refers to a system that does not require a traditional cable to charge. Instead, the device may be placed directly in the charging area, which is a much easier and more efficient method than using wired cables. When charging, the wireless charger interface has a nice appearance and is easily portable. However, the device's overcharging problem is the same regardless of the type of charger used.

Solar Mobile Charger

Solar energy is a "renewable resource" that can be used to fuel electronic devices. One of the most commonly used resources is solar power. One of the successful inventions is solar-powered mobile charging. However, the amount of power produced by a solar panel is highly dependent on the atmosphere in which it is used. Light intensity, time, and position are examples of dependent variables. Solar chargers are a good alternative to regular chargers. It has the advantage of being usable at any time and being compact. It converts solar energy from the sun into electricity using solar panels. However, the device's overcharging problem is the same regardless of the type of charger used.

PROPOSED SYSTEM

The Arduino charging time controller is used to charge your unit for a set period of time. Can

you figure out how it'll happen? Let's see what happens.

This project's most important feature is the Arduino. Aside from that, this project's components are PCB boards, 16 x 2 LCD display, rotary encoder, relay, LED, switchbox. On the PCB board, components such as a 16 x 2 LCD display, LED relay, and Arduino can be mounted. The Rotary Encoder should be set aside so that it can be rotated quickly. The handheld adapter is held outside and is attached to the relay since it is connected to the single socket power outlet. A rotary encoder in the LCD 16 x 2 display is used to set the time at first. The phone is connected to the adapter, which is connected to a single socket power outlet operated by a relay module. So, when the charging time is up, the LCD display shows charged, and the power supply to the battery and charger adapter is disconnected via a relay, with an LED used for indication. While the LED is charging, it is in the off state; once the charging is complete, it is in the on state.

TABLE 1: *The requirement for the model.*

HARDWARE REQUIRED	Arduino Relay LCD display Rotary encoder Power supply Jumper wires Soldering board potentiometer
SOFTWARE REQUIRED	Arduino IDE Tinkercad

BLOCK DIAGRAM

Figure 1: Block Diagram

BLOCK DIAGRAM DESCRIPTION

ARDUINO MICROCONTROLLER

Arduino is an open-source electronics platform that uses simple hardware and software to make it easy to use. Arduino boards can read inputs - such as light from a sensor, a finger on a button, or a Twitter message - and convert them to outputs - such as turning on an LED, triggering a motor, or publishing something online. By sending a series of instructions to the board's microcontroller, you can tell it what to do. The Arduino programming language (based on Wiring) and the Arduino Software (IDE) (based on Processing) are used to accomplish this.

LCD MODULE

LCD (Liquid Crystal Display) is a type of electronic display that can be used in a variety of applications. The name 16x2 LCD display refers to the fact that it has two rows and each row has 16 columns, allowing it to display a maximum of 16 characters per row. A 5x7 pixel matrix is used for each character in a row. Since it is used to represent certain result values, it is used in many applications. For example, to show sensor readings or an output message.

ROTARY ENCODER

The rotary encoder, also known as a shaft position sensor, is an important device for determining position, distance, and speed in a given application. It's an electromechanical system that transforms a shaft's or axis' angular position or movement into analogue or digital outputs. The data in this paper is positioned in a specific column of the LCD display using a rotary encoder. We can walk through the characters on the LCD display by turning the encoder knob. The angular position or motion of a shaft or axle is converted to analogue or digital output signals by a rotary encoder, also known as a shaft encoder.

RELAY

A relay is a type of switch. The flow of charge for the system is initially unavailable in this project, but once the user sets the time, the coil is activated, and the relay makes the flow of charge, switching over automatically when the time reaches 0. The electronic relay is a form of electronic switch that uses electronic components to open or close circuit contacts without requiring any mechanical action.

SOFTWARE

Figure 3: Arduino IDE & Tinkercad

Arduino IDE

The Arduino integrated development environment (IDE) is a piece of software that allows you to work with the Arduino platform. It's a cross-platform application that works on Windows, Linux, and Mac OS X. While this software is written in Java, the Arduino IDE also supports C and C++, all of which have basic syntax and structures. This IDE is simple to use, and you can see the output results in the console window as well as embed the code in the arduino board. Sketches are programmes created with the Arduino Software

(IDE). These sketches were created in a text editor and saved with the.ino file extension. Cutting/pasting, as well as searching/replacing text, are all available in the editor. The message area shows errors and provides input when saving and exporting.

Tinkercad

Tinkercad Circuits is an extension of its design capabilities to include circuits. This adds a whole new dimension to Tinkercad, based on circuit simulation with Arduino. Tinkercad is an excellent online simulation programme. It's especially well suited to Arduino circuits. You can digitally design, code, and compile to see the results before investing in the project. We attempted to incorporate the project's simulation model in this programme.

FLOWCHART

Figure 4: Flow chart of the Proposed System

CIRCUIT DIAGRAM

Figure 5.. Circuit Diagram of the Proposed System

WORKING PRINCIPLE

The read/write pin, data pins, Vcc, and ground pins on the LCD are all properly connected to the microcontroller. The clock pin, data pin, and button pin of the Rotary encoder are attached to Arduino pins 10, 11, and 2. The Arduino pin 12 is attached to the relay input pin. The charging switch box is connected to the Normally open and Common pin. Ground and Vcc pins are connected as needed. When the hardware connections are complete and power is applied to the Arduino board, the LED on the PCB board illuminates, indicating that the board is powered and the LCD display is switched on, displaying the current time state. Initially, the LCD monitor in the 16 x 2 panel displays “HH(hour) MM(minute) SS(second) OK.” You can set the time with the aid of a rotary encoder by spinning the knob and pressing it. First came the hours, then the minutes, and finally the seconds. You can now press OK to correct the time after you've set the necessary time. The procedure starts. It asks for confirmation before charging. 5 seconds are provided in the load current state. If you want to adjust the time, you can press “No” in the load current state, then reset the time and press “Ok.” The relay coil is activated at this stage, and the charging process begins, with the remaining time displayed on the LCD board. The LED on the PCB board also switches off automatically. Second by second, time slows down. When the timer reaches zero, the LCD will display charged, and the state of the relay will

adjust to disconnect the power supply, indicating that the system is now charged.

SIMULATION RESULT:

Figure 6.. Simulation Result of the Proposed System

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This paper, "Simulation of Charging Time Controller using Arduino," was successfully simulated. When the charging time you set in the LCD monitor reaches zero. A relay is used to switch off the power to the charging adapter. As a result, your phone will be paid for the specified amount of time. This prolongs the battery's life and allows you to charge your computer at any time.

CONCLUSION

People are usually busy at work, particularly in the mornings, and they want their phones to be fully charged, so most users plug their phones into the charger before going to bed so that they are fully charged in the morning. Because of the inbuilt software, this overcharging may not cause any problems at first. But, as time goes by, this overcharging decreases the amount of charging cycles and eventually contributes to battery loss. As a result, this project is designed to charge your computer for a fixed period of time, which is beneficial to improving battery life. Since several technologies such as wireless chargers and solar chargers are used, this project aims to extend the device's battery life.

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